

Influence of Automatic Power Regulator of the IBR-2M Pulsed Reactor on Its Dynamics

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, new optimal values of automatic power regulation system parameters were obtained by computational and experimental means using the mathematical model of the IBR-2M pulsed reactor dynamics. Optimality in this case is the ability of the automatic power regulation system to reduce reactor noise in general and especially its low-frequency component. Two variants of operation of the statistically optimal automatic power regulation system of the IBR-2M reactor are considered. For the automatic power regulation system option operating on IBR-2M, in which data averaging with information aging is used, we can see that the power transient parameters strongly depend on the value of the smoothing coefficient q : the quality of the transient process deteriorates as q increases. For the second option of the statistically optimal automatic power regulation system of IBR-2M reactor at constant information value of the controlled parameter N , the calculations show that the optimal value of the coefficient N is in the range of 4-8: neither higher nor lower.

Keywords: IBR-2M, pulsed reactor, automatic power regulator, power feedback, dynamic

1. INTRODUCTION

The IBR-2M pulsed reactor operating at the Laboratory of Neutron Physics of the Joint Institute for Nuclear Research in Dubna, Moscow Region, serves as a neutron source for experiments on derived neutron beams. To stabilize and regulate the average power, the reactor is equipped with an automatic regulation (AR) system. A distinctive feature of IBR-2M operation is the increased level of neutron noise compared to stationary (non-pulsed) reactors. The term "neutron noise" refers to power noise or pulse energy noise. High noise levels (up to 50 % variation with respect to the average value) interfere largely with normal and safe operation of the reactor. Therefore, the investigation and diagnosis of IBR-2M noise has received a lot of attention. The AR system plays an important independent role in this task. In some cases, the operation of the AR system is the only way to correct the level of a particular spectral component of noise. The dynamics of the low-frequency component of the reactor noise ~ 0.1 Hz plays an important role in the safety of IBR-2M. The amplitude of this component grows quite rapidly with power output, but should be limited for safety reasons. The earlier optimization of AR parameters allowed to reduce the growth of low-frequency noise [1]. However, the observed weakening of the power feedback with power output and the increase in associated low-frequency noise required additional AR optimization. In this paper, new optimal values of the AR parameters were obtained by computational and experimental means using the mathematical model of IBR-2M dynamics. Optimality in this case is the ability of the AR system to reduce reactor noise, in general, and especially its low-frequency component.

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2. BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE IBR-2M

The IBR-2M pulsed batch reactor is an upgraded version of the IBR-2 reactor, which was decommissioned in 2006 due to depletion of its service life [2]. The main reactor parameters are given in Table 1. In IBR-2M, periodic narrow reactivity pulses of large amplitude with a period of 0.2 s are created. This is achieved due to the rotation of a movable reflector near the core. The regulators are placed in such a position that the reactor becomes supercritical for short intervals ($\sim 450 \mu\text{s}$) on instantaneous neutrons, while remaining deeply subcritical in the between pulses. As a result, with a period of 0.2 s, the reactor generates powerful neutron pulses (power pulses) with a width of $200 \mu\text{s}$. The vast majority of the total energy released per period (92%) is released in the power pulse, with only 8% (background energy) released between pulses. As a result, the pulse reactor can be represented as a purely pulsed system, and its dynamics can be described by discrete equations.

Table I. Main parameters of the IBR-2M reactor.

Parameter	Value
Average power, MW	2
Fuel	PuO ₂
Number of fuel assemblies	69
Coolant	Na
Nominal value of coolant flow rate, m ³ /h	100
Maximum burnup, %	9
Pulse repetition rate, Hz	5
Pulse half-width of fast neutrons, μs	200
Thermal neutron flux density from moderator surface, n/cm ² ·s:	
time average	$\sim 10^{13}$
burst maximum	$\sim 10^{16}$

3. BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE IBR-2M DYNAMICS MODEL AND FAST POWER FEEDBACK

To estimate the dynamics of the IBR-2M, a mathematical model of the reactor was created [3], [4], [5]. The model allows simulation of power transients as well as frequency analysis in different reactor operating modes. Fig. 1 shows the structural diagram of the IBR-2M dynamics model in the automatic power regulation mode. The model consists of three main parts: a kinetics module, a power feedback (PF) module due to reactor warm-up, and an automatic power regulation (AR) module. In the calculations, the values of the AR module parameters were varied, and transients of pulse energy changes and amplitude-frequency characteristics of the reactor were calculated at different sets of PF parameters. The kinetics module has not been changed. The parameters of the fast PF module were determined experimentally from 2015 to 2021 [6], [7]. The experiments were carried out at different levels of the reactor average power at a constant coolant flow rate through the core equal to 100 m³/h. The transients of pulse energy changes due to rectangular periodic fluctuations of the reactivity were studied. Three characteristic types of transients were identified: stable (A), stable with feedback lag (B), and the third with a significantly oscillatory nature (C) (Fig. 2). In general, the individual components of the PF are nonlinear.

Figure 1. Block-scheme of model dynamics of the IBR-2M with automatic power regulator

Figure 2. Types of recorded transients of relative deviations of the energy of power pulses IBR-2M (1 – experiment, 2 – simulation) in the self-regulation mode with rectangular fluctuations of the setting reactivity (3) for three sets of PF parameters (a-c) corresponding to A, B, C. t - time

4. STRUCTURE OF AUTOMATIC POWER REGULATION UNIT OF IBR-2M AND STATISTICALLY OPTIMAL CONTROL ALGORITHM

The IBR-2M automatic power regulator is based on a statistically optimal algorithm. The detailed derivation of the statistically optimal AR algorithm for IBR-2M is given in [8]. Here we consider its brief summary. The statistically optimal algorithm provides a minimum of the likely RMS relative energy deviation of a future (n -th) power pulse based on information obtained from previous (k -th) power pulses ($k < n$). In the current AR system, information from previous pulses is given different weights and thus introduces the principle of information aging. As a result, the optimal AR algorithm takes the form of [9]:

$$\Delta r_{An} = \frac{1}{\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} a_{n-k}^2} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} a_{n-k}^2 (\Delta r_{Ak} - \Delta e_{pk}) \quad (1)$$

where Δr_{An} , Δr_{Ak} are deviations of AR reactivity from the average (basic) level expressed in fractions of β_p , referring to the future (n -th) and preceding (k -th) power pulses, respectively, Δe_{pk} are relative energy deviations of preceding power pulses ($k = 0$ corresponds to the beginning of information collecting by the automatic regulator unit), $a_{n-k}^2 \leq 1$ is the parameter depending on the difference of pulse numbers $n - k \geq 1$, characterizes the degree of information aging from preceding power pulses.

Equation (1) for an impulse system relates the AR output signal Δr_{An} in the future (n -th) pulse to the values of the AR input signal $(\Delta r_{Ak} - \Delta e_{pk})$, corresponding to the previous pulses with numbers

$k = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1$, and to the discrete values of the impulse transient response of the AR $w_{An-k} = \left(\frac{1}{\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} a_{n-k}^2}\right) a_{n-k}^2$. It follows from equation (1) that the impulse response of the AR, that is, the response of the AR to a unit pulse applied to the AR at the moment corresponding to the pulse with the number $m = 0$, is described by the expression

$$w_{An} = \frac{1}{\sum_{m=1}^n a_m^2} \sum_{m=1}^n a_m^2, \quad (2)$$

where $n \geq 1$.

Thus, the impulse response and therefore the structure of the AR is determined by the choice of the function a_{n-k}^2 in equation (1). In IBR-2M it is accepted that earlier information is given less weight, as the index $n - k$ increases, the parameter a_{n-k}^2 decreases ($a_0^2 = 1 > a_1^2 > a_2^2 > \dots$). The function a_{n-k}^2 is described by a decreasing exponent:

$$a_{n-k}^2 = \exp\left(-\frac{(n-k)T_p}{T_A}\right), \quad (3)$$

where T_p is the period of power pulses, T_A is the time constant of the exponential function a_{n-k}^2 . From formula (3) it follows that starting from the pulse number $n > 5T_A/T_p$, the sum $\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} a_{n-k}^2$ in algorithm (1) can be considered as a constant value. Taking this into account, the impulse response of AR (2) of the IBR-2M takes the following form:

$$w_{An} = \left(1 - e^{-\frac{T_p}{T_A}}\right) \sum_{m=1}^n e^{-\frac{mT_p}{T_A}}. \quad (4)$$

This is the impulse response of an aperiodic link with the pulse transfer function

$$W_A^*(z) = \frac{\Delta r_A(z)}{\delta_A(z)} = \left(1 - e^{-\frac{T_p}{T_A}}\right) \frac{z^{-1}}{1 - e^{-\frac{T_p}{T_A}} z^{-1}}, \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta r_A(z)$ and $\delta_A(z)$ are, respectively, z -images of the output and input signals of the AR, considered as functions different from zero only at the moments of appearance of power pulses. With the ratio $T_A \gg T_p$, the function (5) takes the form of an integrator pulse function:

$$W_A^*(z) = \frac{\Delta r_A(z)}{\delta_A(z)} = \frac{T_p}{T_A} \frac{z^{-1}}{1 - z^{-1}}. \quad (6)$$

The AR of IBR-2M represents just such an integrator.

The value T_A can be set differently, for which the ratio $T_A = 10\Delta$, where Δ is the parameter to be varied, is used. Currently, it is accepted $\Delta = 0.2$, that is, $T_A = 2$ and the AR transfer coefficient in equation (6) is equal to $T_p/T_A = 0.1$. Δ is the AR speed parameter: the larger it is, the lower is the AR speed at the same signal at its input.

4.1. The First Option for Smoothing the Controlled Parameter.

Two algorithms for smoothing the controlled parameter were considered: the first one with information aging, currently used in the IBR-2M AR system, and the second one with equal information weight - a statistically optimal algorithm potentially applicable to the IBR-2M.

The controlled parameter Δe_{pn} is passed through an additional filter introduced and transformed into a smoothed signal $\Delta \tilde{e}_{pn}$. As a result, a smoothed signal $\delta_{An} = \Delta \tilde{e}_{pn}$ is fed to the AR input. The smoothing algorithm satisfies the statistically optimal criterion [10] and is expressed by the following equation.

$$\Delta \tilde{e}_{pn} = \Delta \tilde{e}_{pn-1} + \frac{1}{q}(\Delta e_{pn} - \Delta \tilde{e}_{pn-1}). \quad (7)$$

where $q > 1$ is the smoothing coefficient (when $q = 1$, $\Delta \tilde{e}_{pn} = \Delta e_{pn}$ the filter does not work and smoothing of the controlled parameter is not performed). The pulse transfer function corresponds to the filter with algorithm (7)

$$W_{\sim}^*(z) = \frac{\Delta \tilde{e}_p(z)}{\Delta e_p(z)} = \frac{1}{q-1} \cdot \frac{1}{q-1 - z^{-1}}. \quad (8)$$

The structural diagram of the closed-loop automatic regulation system of IBR-2M with this option of smoothing of the controlled parameter is shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Schema of the closed-loop automatic regulation system of IBR-2M. W_A^* , W_R^* , W_{\sim}^* are pulsed transfer functions of the AR, reactor and filter, respectively, Δr_{Fn} – the external reactivity disturbance

4.2. The Second Option for Smoothing the Controlled Parameter.

Only information from the N preceding power pulses is considered and given the highest weight ($a_{n-k}^2 = 1$ at $1 \leq n-k \leq N$ and $a_{n-k}^2 = 0$ at $n-k > N$). The following statistically optimal AR algorithm corresponds to this case

$$\Delta r_{An} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^N (\Delta r_{An-k} - \Delta e_{pn-k})}{N}. \quad (9)$$

Thus, the output signal of the AR is the arithmetic mean of N preceding input signals. It follows from equation (9) that the pulse transfer function of the AR is equal to

$$W_{A2}^* = \frac{\Delta r_A(z)}{\Delta e_p(z)} = \frac{z^{-1} (1 - z^{-N})}{N (1 - z^{-1})}. \quad (10)$$

Figure 4. Closed-loop control system of the IBR-2M reactor with equal information weights of the controlled parameter. W_{A2}^* , W_R^* , are pulsed transfer functions of the AR and reactor, respectively, Δr_{Fn} – the external reactivity disturbance

Below, in Section 5, the dynamics of IBR-2M is analyzed with the selection of optimal AR parameters.

5. ANALYSIS OF IBR-2M DYNAMICS UNDER VARYING AR PARAMETERS. SELECTION OF OPTIMAL PARAMETER VALUES

For the IBR-2M AR with the PF parameters corresponding to the typical transients given in Fig. 2, the power transients in the AR mode are modeled. Modeling was carried out at reactivity perturbation in the form of a jump of $0.1 \beta_p$ at the standard value of the parameter $\Delta = 0.2$ and values of the filter smoothing coefficient q in the range from 1 to 8 (Fig.5).

Figure 5. Transients of the IBR-2M power change during a reactivity jump of $0.1 \beta_p$ in the regime with AR for three sets of PF parameters (a-c) corresponding to A, B, C. Smoothing coefficient of AR q equal to 2 (1), 4 (2) and 8 (3). t - time

As a result of processing the data presented in Fig. 5, the main transient quality indicators were evaluated: transient durations $t_{s,t.}$ and damping decrements χ depending on the value of the smoothing coefficient q . The response time (transient duration $t_{s,t.}$) was defined as the minimum time for which the controlled parameter Δe_{pn} with the required accuracy will become close to the target value Δe_p^0 . The smaller this value is, the better. The decay decrement characterizes the magnitude of the amplitude drop during half of the oscillation period. The greater the decrement, the better. Quality indicators of transient power change depending on the value of smoothing factor q are shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6. The main indicators of the quality of power transients with a reactivity jump of $0.1 \beta_p$, depending on the value of the smoothing coefficient q : a) settling time of power transients (transient durations) $t_{s,t.}$, b) damping decrement χ . A, B and C correspond to three sets of PF parameters. The red vertical dashed line corresponds to the currently valid q value, the green one is a promising candidate.

Fig.7 shows the amplitude-frequency responses of IBR-2M, corresponding to three options of transients (Fig.5), at different values of the smoothing factor q from 1 to 8.

Fig. 8 shows the transient quality indices in IBR-2M using statistically optimal AR with data averaging with equal information weights, i.e., the results of the analysis for the second option of smoothing the controlled parameter are presented (see the previous Section 4).

Figure 7. Color map of the amplitude-frequency response of the IBR-2M in regime with AR dependence on smoothing coefficient q for three sets of PF parameters (a-c) corresponding to A, B, C. The red horizontal dashed line corresponds to the currently valid q value, the white one is a promising candidate. A clear resonance is visible in the frequency range of 0.1-0.2 Hz in the stabilization working area

Figure 8. The main indicators of the quality of power transients with a reactivity jump of $0.1 \beta_p$, depending on the coefficient value of new AR N : a) settling time of power transients (transient durations) $t_{s.t.}$, b) damping decrement χ . A, B and C correspond to three sets of PF parameters. The shaded area is the area of optimal values of N with the center $N = 6$

6. CONCLUSIONS

Two variants of operation of the statistically optimal automatic regulator (AR) of the IBR-2M reactor are considered. For the AR option operating on IBR-2M, in which data averaging with information aging is used, we can see that the power transient parameters strongly depend on the value of the smoothing coefficient q : the quality of the transient process deteriorates as q increases. This is clearly observed for all reactor operating modes at different energy output levels, except for "zero" (fresh fuel). For fresh fuel, the transient duration with changing q is almost unchanged and the decrement of damping is maximum. The reactor state during this period of its operation corresponded to a rather high value of the total fast PF coefficient $k_T = -5.14 \beta_p / \text{MW}$. At this value k_T , the low-frequency oscillation of the reactor is minimal [11]. Thus, in a reactor with fresh fuel, the transient quality indicators are the best, but, as can be seen from the data presented above, these indicators deteriorate with energy output. The best q values for the AR system operating at the reactor are in the range of 2-4. Currently, the value

of q is 4, i.e., there is some prospect of improving the noise state of IBR-2M by moving the number of averages q to a value of 2. For the second option of the statistically optimal AR of IBR-2M at constant information value of the controlled parameter N , the calculations show that the optimal value of the coefficient N is in the range of 4-8: neither higher nor lower.

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